

ACTION OF SULPHUR DIOXIDE WATER ON AMMONIUM PERMANGANATE

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The action of sulphur dioxide water (sulphurous acid) on ammonium permanganate tends to the formation of a dark brown precipitate of the general composition: x $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{O}$, y MnO , z MnO_2 . The filtrate shows distinctly acidic reactions due to the presence of sulphuric acid formed during the reaction. Ammonium sulphate, manganese sulphate and ammonium dithionate are the various products of reaction.

The dark brown precipitate, when sulphurous acid is further added, is completely redissolved, the reaction at this stage being represented by the equation:

In a previous communication (Lal and Singh, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 547) the action of sulphurous acid on calcium permanganate has been reported. The present work includes the study of the action of sulphurous acid on ammonium permanganate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium permanganate was prepared by dissolving KMnO_4 of A.R. quality (16 g.) in distilled water (300 c.c.) at 70° and mixing it with a solution of NH_4Cl (A.R., 44 g.) in distilled water (300 c.c.), and concentrating the volume to about 200 c.c. It was cooled to 0° with ice, when long needle-shaped crystals of ammonium permanganate were obtained which were filtered in a sintered glass crucible, washed with distilled water three to four times and recrystallised from distilled water thrice (Moles and Crespi, *Anal. Soc. espan. Fis. quim.*, 1922, 20, 555). These crystals without drying were dissolved in water and made up to a known volume. On qualitative analysis the solution was found to be free from K^+ and Cl^- . The purity was further tested by determining MnO_4^- by titrating against a standard solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate (A.R.), and NH_4^+ by Kjeldahl's method (Swift, "A System of Chemical Analysis", 1940, pp. 404-406). Both these values agreed with the formula $(\text{NH}_4)\text{MnO}_4$ within 0.5% error. For each duplicate set, a fresh sample of ammonium permanganate was prepared, analysed and diluted to make it 0.5% solution likewise.

Sulphur dioxide gas was prepared by dropping H_2SO_4 (dil.) on potassium bisulphite. Sulphurous acid was prepared by bubbling this gas through a dark coloured ground-glass stoppered bottle filled with distilled water to the brim and surrounded by ice. It was titrated against a standard alkali solution quickly and then diluted with distilled water till it was normal (approx.). To have comparatively the same strength of the acid, a fresh sample was prepared every time. The oxidation of sulphur dioxide in solution was avoided by protecting it from direct exposure and by conducting the whole experiment in the shortest possible time. Some loss of sulphur dioxide due to volatilisation was always unavoidable, but no sulphate formation was detected in the sample of sulphurous acid.

The normal sulphurous acid, thus prepared, was added dropwise from the burette to ammonium permanganate solution (100 c.c., 0.5%), taken in two separate beakers, till the pink colour was just discharged. The precipitate at this stage of the reaction, *i.e.* the intermediate stage, after separating from the filtrate, was found to contain manganese dioxide, manganous oxide and ammonia. Presence of any sulphur acid was not detected in the precipitate. The oxides of manganese were determined by the methods used by Lal and Singh (*loc. cit.*) and ammonia by Kjeldahl's method. The analytical results (Table I) indicate the molar ratio between $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, MnO and MnO_2 as 1 : 1 : 7.

The filtrate indicated the presence of NH_4^+ , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and H_2SO_4 . Traces of Mn^{2+} were also suspected in the filtrate. NH_4^+ was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and the rest of the reaction products by the methods used previously. In the filtrate, which was acidic, NH_4^+ was accounted for as SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. The Mn^{2+} content of the filtrate was very small and was determined by difference.

The decolorisation stage of the reaction was studied with the increasing volumes of normal sulphurous acid. The various analytical values are recorded in Table I. In the final stage (Expt. No. 6) NH_4^+ was accounted for both as sulphate and dithionate, and Mn^{2+} as sulphate only.

To study the preliminary stage of the reaction, more experiments in duplicate were repeated with three-fourth and half of the volume of sulphurous acid required for the intermediate stage. The amounts of various reaction products and the percentage decomposition of ammonium permanganate are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Total Mn^{2+} added = 0.2007 g. Total NH_4^+ added = 0.0657 g.							
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Expt. No.	H_2SO_3 added.	NH_4MnO_4 decomp.	Filtrate				Precipitate
			$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$	MnSO_4	H_2SO_4	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}:\text{MnO}:\text{MnO}_2$ (mol. ratio).
1	6.00 c.c.	54.84%	0.11066 g.	0.00349 g.	Nil	0.1438 g.	1:2.43:10.09
	6.00	54.64	0.11056	0.004012		0.1445	1:2.30:9.88
2	9.00	77.32	0.1386	0.00546	„	0.2934	1:1.39:7.06
	9.00	77.23	0.1368	0.00638		0.2934	1:1.34:6.86
3	12.10	100	0.1741	0.00786	0.00586 g.	0.3875	1:1.16:6.55
	12.10		0.17724	0.00796	0.00604	0.3869	1:1.33:7.23
4	14.60	„	0.1745	0.0518	0.08648	0.4060	1:2.75:9.65
	14.60		0.1734	0.05396	0.08782	0.4037	1:2.94:10.17
5	17.10	„	0.17485	0.08723	0.1992	0.3967	1:13.24:20.52
	17.10		0.17456	0.08581	0.2018	0.3990	1:12.59:20.86
6	21.40	„	0.17384	0.10082	0.5510	0.3453	Nil
	21.40		0.17479	0.09942	0.5510	0.3453	

DISCUSSION

About 80% of sulphurous acid added is converted into other sulphur acids (SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$) and the rest is lost by volatilisation during the preparation and addition of sul

phurous acid. Regarding the formation of various sulphur acids in the filtrate, the results are in agreement with those already obtained when normal sulphurous acid is allowed to react with calcium permanganate solution (*loc.cit.*). In the final stage (Expt. No. 6), the reaction is represented as

The value of the mol. ratio $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} : \text{MnO} : \text{MnO}_2$ in the intermediate stage is 1:1:7 as against 1:2:13 in the case of calcium permanganate ($\text{CaO}, 2\text{MnO}, 13\text{MnO}_2$). A similar complex is formed in Expt. 2 while the composition changes to 1:3:10 and 1:13:21 in Expts. 4 and 5. The difference between the calcium and the ammonium complexes in the corresponding stages is probably due to their different basic character.

According to Biltz (*Gott. Nachr.*, 1930, 189) hydrated manganese dioxide may be regarded as permanganous acid, H_2MnO_3 , so that manganese dioxide becomes permanganous anhydride, and the salts $\text{RO} \cdot n\text{MnO}_2$, permanganites. According to Groger (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1862, *iii*, 66, 161) these permanganites may be regarded as the various derivatives of hydrated manganese dioxide.

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